

Participants	Explanation	Examples
Businesses		IBM
Citizen science		
Civil Servants		Civil Servants, Public administrators, Politicians
Data Scientists		
Domain experts	Users with domain specific knowledge	
Government agencies		
Hackathon Participants		
Infomediaries	Intermediate entities that offer services based on open data to end users	Companies or groups offering improved open data as a service, either by bundling it or providing processed data
Journalists		
Legal advisors	Users versed in legal questions	
Mediators	Mediators between disciplines	
NGOs		
Open data experts	Users who are mainly interested in the open aspect of data, less in the domain it covers	
Organisations		Associations, Clubs
Private Citizens	Politically motivated citizens	Civic hackers, transparency advocates
Researchers		
Software Developers		
Startups/Entrepreneurs		
Students	Students during university courses or experiments	